

Optimizing Parameterization

bwRSE4HPC Project Proposal

Assigned RSEs:	Glen Hunter ¹ , Marcel Koch ²
Project Partners:	Alexander Zirn ³
Scientific field:	Chemical Engineering
Subfield:	Chemical Reaction Engineering
Start:	2025-04-13
Duration:	10 weeks
Type of Work:	Parallelization, HPC Porting
License:	TBD
Link:	https://gitlab.uni-ulm.de/ciw-ag-g-ttel/private/institute-members/dyn_meth_AZA_optimized
Programming Language:	Python
Technologies:	SciPy, multiprocessing, Dask (if HPC scaling required)
Target Cluster:	JUSTUS 2

1. Project Summary

With the continued increase in global temperatures due to climate change, society is investing more into renewable sources of energy. A key issue with renewable energy is how best to store the excess energy that is produced. One such method that is being investigated is to synthesize methane (CH₄) by electrolyzing water to form molecular hydrogen (H₂) and reacting it with carbon dioxide (CO₂) in a Sabatier reactor.

Alexander Zirn is creating a digital twin of the Sabatier reactor, creating parametrized microkinetic models of this experiment [1]. This requires fitting models to experimental data to find optimal parameters for the reactor mass balance. There are many degrees of freedom that can be explored and as a result finding parameters can take a long time, upwards of 12 hours for 18 parameters on a laptop. The project partner is looking for ways to improve the performance of their parameterization code.

2. Problem Statement

The code is divided into three main classes:

- Reactor_input - loads the experimental residence time data (RTD) and the mechanistic model and then generates and solves the mass balance equations.
- Output - Convolves the result with the downstream RTD generated from a previous experiment [2].

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- Optimizer - Subclass of Output. Fits a model to the experimental results and optimizes the resulting parameters for that model. The optimization algorithm use a Basin Hopping algorithm of SciPy to search the parameters space, with Nelder-Mead algorithm for further local minimization.

The optimization step is the bottle neck for creating the parametrized models due to the number of parameters that need to be considered. If more parameters are to be considered in the future, a more efficient version of the optimizer needs to be established.

3. Suggested Solution

The current approach for optimization with SciPy does not make use of parallelization. By default, SciPy performs any functions with single-thread execution, however some functions can be parallelized by providing the number of threads/processes to workers parameter of the function. Since SciPy and its dependencies take most of their performance from compiled low-level libraries, like BLAS and LAPACK, it also must be ensured that those are optimally installed. If the Basin Hopping algorithm does not take the workers parameter, then a different approach is needed. One such approach as described in Carmona et al. 2025 [3] would be to perform the Basin Hopping algorithm such that multiple perturbations are considered at each iteration by running the local minimization in parallel.

The Basin Hopping algorithm with Nelder-Mead local minimization is not the only parameterization method that can be used. At the request of the project partner, a small test environment will be created to allow for the user to experiment with different minimization functions.

In addition to making the code fast with the use of parallelization, the code repository can be modified to introduce standard software engineering practices should the project partner be interested. This would include the following:

- making use of pyproject.yaml files and lock files to ensure the correct dependencies.
- establishing the repository on a forge of choice (GitHub or institute GitLab).
- introducing a continuous integration (CI) pipeline to ensure standard practices are followed during development.
- creating a testing framework.

Optionally, in case of packaging the code:

- refactoring of some code to remove repeating of variables and improve readability.
- variable typing.
- documentation.

4. Milestones

- Week 1: Establish the repository with base CI pipeline and Python dependencies, making use of pyproject.yaml and lock files.
- Week 2: Setup SciPy with the optimized dependencies.
- Week 3 & 4: Implement new parallelized optimization method.
- Week 5 & 6: Create testing environment to test different minimization methods.
- Week 7 & 8: Refactoring existing code to include typing.
- Week 9 onwards: Develop testing framework with basic unit test and integration tests.

5. Deliverables

The assigned RSEs will deliver a repository with the parallelized optimization implemented as described in the suggested solutions. Optionally, if the project partners request, the code will contain the relevant refactoring and variable typing in line with Python standards. In addition, the RSEs will introduce dependency control for the code. A working CI pipeline with both unit and integration tests will be created. Should the project partner wish to release the code as a small Python package, additional documentation will be provided.

6. Expected Contributions

The project partners will contribute the following:

- access to the code with examples for the RSEs to perform initial testing with.
- provide answers to any questions that the RSEs have regarding the code.
- participation in update meetings.
- acknowledgement or co-authorship on subsequent publication that makes use of the features developed by the RSEs.

Bibliography

- [1] A. Zirn, A. P. G. Baade, H. Stagge, K. Ray, and R. Güttel, “Extending the Periodic Transient Kinetics Method by Techniques resolving Surface Reaction Intermediates,” *ChemRxiv*, vol. 2026, no. 226, p. , 2026, doi: [10.26434/chemrxiv.15000434/v1](https://doi.org/10.26434/chemrxiv.15000434/v1) .
- [2] H. Stagge, M. Gäßler, T. Oyuncu, and R. Güttel, “nRTD: Determining complex residence time distributions from experimental data using convolutional neural networks,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 320, p. 122454, 2026, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2025.122454> .
- [3] O. Carmona, P. L. Rodríguez-Kessler, S. Salazar-Colores, and A. Muñoz-Castro, “Revisiting and Accelerating the Basin Hopping Algorithm for Lennard-Jones Clusters: Adaptive and Parallel Implementation in Python.” [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2510.25938>